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A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF HUMAN HEMODYNAMICS FOR USE IN SPECIAL SOFTWARE SIMULATING PILOTS' PHYSIOLOGICAL RESPONSES TO SUSTAINED $\pm G_z$ ACCELERATIONS

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Abstract

A quantitative model (QM) of human hemodynamics describing the influences of gravity and extravascular pressure on blood flow is proposed. QM is a basis for creating special software that simulates the main physiological responses to dynamic $\pm G_z$ accelerations. In QM, a sitting person's cardiovascular system (CVS) is presented by a set of arterial and venous compartments localized at different distances from the horizontal level. Functions of the right and left ventricles are modeled as transformers of input pressure to output blood flow. Heart rate and ventricles' contractility are under sympathetic and parasympathetic control. Sympathetic influences modify compliance and unstressed volume of every vascular compartment. Both ascending impulses that come from vascular mechanoreceptors and descending impulses of supra-bulbar neuronal centers affect the sympathetic and parasympathetic control of CVS. By algorithms altering local extravascular pressure, QM can imitate the hemodynamic effects of standard protective tools (muscle stress, pneumatic or liquid G-suits, and breathing through a mask under excess pressure). QM also simulates hemodynamic effects caused by changes in the direction of the acceleration vector. Body weight and length, sex, age, physical and emotional states, acceleration profiles, and characteristics of protective tools are input variables of QM. The output variables are blood pressures, flows, and volumes in the brain, eyes, lungs, abdominal section, hands, thighs, and legs.

Keywords: fighter pilot, training, centrifuge, testing, aero-combat maneuvers, G-LOC.

Introduction

Maneuvers on modern fighter aircraft are associated with rapid altering and sustained extreme accelerations [1-3]. Both physiological [4-9] and biotechnical [10-12] problems that arose in parallel with an increase in military aircraft's maneuverability have been properly investigated [4-18]. Human physiology evolutionarily adapted to the one g Earth environment, cannot provide adequate functioning of the brain and eyes of a sitting person under extreme accelerations: the hydrostatic pressure proportional to the acceleration value expands the vascular wall, accumulating greater blood volume. The altered pressure gradients do not provide the necessary circulation at the cardiovascular scale. Accelerations also alter the ventilation-perfusion ratio in the lungs [13,14].

Most critical are positive (+G_z) accelerations acting in the direction of head-legs, or negative (-G_z) accelerations acting in the opposite direction [4-6]. In terminal zones (brain, eyes), the lowered circulation causes oxygen lack and worsens the pilot's vision and consciousness [9,12]. Under -G_z, the elevated local blood pressure in the eyes and brain causes rupture of microscopic vessels and hemorrhages. An essential role in these events is the value of G_z and the gradient of acceleration change.

Under relatively slow (0.1-0.4 g/sec) linearly increasing +G_z accelerations, a mean healthy person not using artificial protections is operable for approximately +4G_z accelerations [11]. Further elevation of the G-load causes the G-LOC phenomenon which usually disappears after a break [2,6,8]. Modern fighter air-

craft (like F16, F35, and others) can provide acceleration gradients exceeding 2 g/sec. This requires special protection algorithms and devices. Typical protection algorithms include special pneumatic or water-augmented anti-G suits, muscle stress, and breathing with positive pressure air [1,11,17]. The adaptive protection algorithms combining multiple methods depending on the dynamics of accelerations are the most effective. Traditionally, empiric research on centrifuges is the main way to invent more effective protections [1,5,6-8]. Special software simulators based on quantitative mathematical models provide additional ways to maximize the individual resistance of a pilot to the negative effects of accelerations [18-20]. A model of the cardiovascular system (CVS) is at the core of quantitative models.

The goal of this article is to present the model of CVS.

Modeling of human hemodynamics

Organs and anatomical-functional systems function as parts of a whole and very complex biological mechanism. Each mathematical model is only a simplified version of this complex mechanism. The model has its distinguishing characteristics and limitations associated with the main assumptions. In our case, extreme alterations and the rapid dynamics of events are the most distinguishing factors to be duly modeled. Therefore, it is important to analyze both the initial physical effects of accelerations and the main physiological mechanisms involved in the organism's responses to these effects.

1. Physiological background

The two most distinguishable characteristics of pilotage accelerations are 1) a short duration and high dynamism; and 2) the intensity of local forces is proportional to the distance from the heart. So, reflector mechanisms are the main providers of an organism's physiological responses to altered hemodynamics. Mechanoreceptors of CVS, sensing the altered local mechanical forces, provide bulbar neurons in the brain with ascending impulse patterns. Changes in efferent

impulse patterns in sympathetic and parasympathetic nerves are neuronal centers' response to the ascending information. These nerves have branches in the heart while the vasculature has only sympathetic innervation. The density of regional sympathetic innervation in the body's lower part is almost proportional to the distance of the vascular compartment from the heart. Namely, this physiological knowledge is realized in the model part, presenting the central control of human hemodynamics (see Fig.1).

Fig.1. Schematic structure of the model presenting the central nervous control of CVS.

Heart rate ($F(t)$) and contractility ($k(t)$), regional vascular rigidities ($D_i(t)$), and unstressed volumes ($U_i(t)$) are the output variables of the central regulator (the medulla oblongata). It is under ascending and descending impulse patterns. Sources for the ascending pattern are cardiovascular mechanoreceptors being under mean transmural pressures in brain arteria of Willis circle ($P_{ba}(t)$), carotid sinuses ($P_c(t)$), aortic arch ($P_a(t)$), and right atria ($P_v(t)$). Sources for the descending pattern are upper brain neuronal centers integrating impulses from proprioceptors, eyes, and internal glands producing hormones.

Factors forming driving forces in the human vascular net are associated with local extravascular pressures. They depend on the elasticity of surrounding tissues or cavities in which the vascular compartment is located. In skeletal muscles, the local extravascular pressure increases in parallel with muscle stress. The

volumes of blood and cerebrospinal fluid are the two main determinants of the dynamics of extravascular pressure in the rigid cranial cavity. In the thorax, the dynamics of the extravascular pressure depend on pleural pressure altering in association with breath. An elastic diaphragm separates the thoracic and abdominal cavities. Therefore, respiratory fluctuations in pleural pressure affect extravascular pressure in the abdominal cavity. Changes in local external pressure on the abdominal muscle are an additional modulator of pleural pressure. For the skin vasculature, the extravascular pressure is either atmospheric pressure (default) or the pressure in the anti-G suit.

Biomechanical events to be modeled have two components: biological, and artificial. Specific suits that act against vision loss and so-called G-LOC represent the main artificial components [33]. The gravitational factor (here accelerations) modulates the hydrostatic component of the blood pressure: the effect is

proportional to the distance between the so-called hydrostatic indifferent point (approximately located at the heart level) and the vascular compartment. Therefore, the model of CVS must reflect the real size of the vascular net and main sectional peculiarities (see Fig.2). Since the ventilation-perfusion ratios in different parts

of the lungs change with changes in the gravitational factor, the pulmonary vascular network is represented in the model at three levels. The effect caused by the difference in the location of the atria and ventricles is modeled too.

Fig.2. Model presentation of CVS

Compartments are located on different levels. Specific extravascular environments in body sections are also taken into account. Right and left compartments of the heart are presented by atria and ventricles. Lung vascular net is presented on three levels.

In fig.2, horizontal lines conventionally reflect the fact that the vasculature of body different regions is working in environments that have specific different physical characteristics. Brain vasculature, presented with three compartments, is located in a rigid cranium. Besides, brain arterioles have an autonomous neural

mechanism providing practical stable total flow despite wide range of perfusion pressure alterations. The atmospheric pressure is the extravascular pressure for vascular compartments of neck, and skin vessels of arms and legs. Muscle pressure is the extravascular pressure for vascular compartments of muscles. Thoracic and abdominal pressures are the extravascular pressures for vascular compartments of these body sections.

2.A model of the heart

In the heart model, stroke volumes $V_{sri}(t)$ of the right ($i = 1$), and left ($i = 2$) ventricles depend on input pressures $P_{vi}(t)$, unstressed volumes $U_{vi}(t)$, du-

ration of diastolic phase $T_d(t)$, chamber's end-diastolic rigidity D_i , resistance of opened atrioventricular valves r_i^{av} , and pressure gradients between atria and ventricle ΔP_{ai}^V .

$$V_{sri}(t) = \frac{(U_i(t) + \Delta P_{ai}^V(t) / D_i(t)) - U_0}{(1 - e^{-\frac{T_d(t) \cdot D_i(t)}{r_i^{av}}})}.$$

$$\Delta P_{ai}^V(t) = P_i^{In}(t) + 0,735 \cdot \rho \cdot h_{vi}^a \cdot n(t) \cdot \cos(A_{ch}(t)),$$

where P_i^{In} is the input pressure, h_{vi}^a is the distance between mean levels of atria and ventricles, $n(t)$ is acceleration value, $A_{ch}(t)$ is the angle between armchair and vertical, ρ is blood density, U_0 is approximation parameter.

Pressures in each heart chamber ($P_V(t)$) are calculated according to piecewise linear approximation:

$$P_i^I(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & V_i(t) < U_i(t) \\ (V_i(t) - U_i(t)) \cdot D_i(t), & U_i(t) \leq V_i(t) < U1_i(t) \\ (U1_i(t) - U_i(t)) \cdot D_i(t) + (V_i(t) - U1_i(t)) \cdot D1_i(t), & U1_i(t) < V_i(t) \end{cases}.$$

Cardiac output $Q_i^{Ou}(t)$ is calculated as:

$$Q_i^{Ou}(t) = F(t) \cdot V_{sri}(t).$$

Volumes of heart chambers are calculated using equation below:

$$V_i(t) = V_i(0) + \int_{t-h}^t (Q_i^{In} - Q_i^{Ou}) dt,$$

where $Q_i^{In}(t)$ represent input flows into heart chambers.

3.A model of the vascular hemodynamics

In the model of vascular hemodynamics, each vascular compartment has its unstressed volume ($U_i(t)$), volume ($V_i(t)$), volumetric rigidity ($D_i(t)$), internal pressure ($P_i^I(t)$), external pressure ($P_i^E(t)$), length ($L_i(t)$), and angle relatively to horizon ($A_i(t)$).

$$P_i^I(t) = \begin{cases} (V_i(t) - U_i(t)) \cdot D_i^N(t), & V_i(t) < U_i(t) \\ (V_i(t) - U_i(t)) \cdot D_i(t), & U_i(t) \leq V_i(t) < U1_i(t) \\ (U1_i(t) - U_i(t)) \cdot D_i(t) + (V_i(t) - U1_i(t)) \cdot D1_i(t), & U1_i(t) < V_i(t) \end{cases}$$

A blood flow between i and $R_{i,i+1}(t) = R_{i,i+1}(V_i = U_i) \cdot (U_i / V_i(t))^2$ vascular compartments is calculated as:

$$Q_{i,i+1}(t) = (P_i(t) + P_i^E(t) + n \cdot \rho \cdot L_i(t) \cdot \sin(A_i(t))) - (P_{i+1}(t) + P_{i+1}^E(t) + n \cdot \rho \cdot L_{i+1}(t) \cdot \sin(A_{i+1}(t))) / R_{i,i+1}(t),$$

where $R_{i,i+1}(t)$ is the hydraulic resistance between the neighbor vascular compartments.

$$R_{i,i+1}(t) = R_{i,i+1(V_i=U_i)} \cdot (U_i(t) / V_i(t))^2.$$

Brain circulation is specific by two reasons. First, the brain is located in a rigid cranium. Second, brain is immersed in a cerebral-spinal liquid (liquor) that during short-time observations like those under dynamic accelerations has a constant volume, while intravascular blood volume is highly variable. Besides, it is well-known that within intervals of pressure in brain arteries of $50 < (P_{ba}(t) - P_L(t)) < 150 \text{ mmHg}$, total brain flow ($q_{ba}(t)$) is provided by the autonomic mechanism. Taking into account this self-regulation, dynamics of $q_{ba}(t)$ modeled by a differential equation:

$$T_{ba} \frac{dr_{ba}}{dt} = \delta \cdot (P_{ba}(t) - P_L(t)) - r_{ba}(t),$$

where $P_L(t)$ is the liquor pressure, T_{ba} - the time constant of this autonomic nervous regulation. Out of self-regulation intervals, $r_{ba}(t)$ is given as:

$$r_{ba}(t) = \begin{cases} r_{ba}^{\min}, & (P_{ba}(t) - P_L(t)) \leq 50 \text{ mmHg} \\ r_{ba}^{\max}, & (P_{ba}(t) - P_L(t)) \geq 150 \text{ mmHg} \end{cases}.$$

Dynamics of blood volumes in every vascular compartment are calculated as:

$$V_i(t) = V_i(t-h) + \int_{t-h}^t (q_i(t) - q_{i+1}(t)) dt.$$

Taking into account the short duration of accelerations, the total blood volume ($V_T(t)$) is assumed to be constant:

$$V_T(t) = \sum_i V_i(t) = \text{const}.$$

4. A model of the CVS's physiological control

The model of physiological control of hemodynamics describes functions of all three blocks (afferent, central, and efferent) of nervous-reflector mechanisms based on information presented by cardiovascular mechanoreceptors (baroreceptors). The model describes integral characteristics of multi-fiber sensitive nerves. As receptors of each zone react to stretch caused by local blood transmural pressure, each receptors zone has its own parameters of activation threshold (P_j^t) and saturation pressures (P_j^s). Functions of multi-fiber nerves, ascending from different zones of CVS's mechanoreceptors, are modeled with uniform and normalized within a scale of [0-1] static S-form dependencies between local transmural pressure ($\Delta P_j(t)$) and afferent activities ($N_\Sigma(t)$):

$$N_j(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \Delta P_j(t) \leq 0 \\ (1 - e^{-\alpha \cdot \Delta P_j(t)}) / (1 + \beta \cdot e^{-\alpha \cdot \Delta P_j(t)}), & 0 < \Delta P_j(t) \leq P_j^s \quad (j = \overline{1, 4}), \\ 1, & \Delta P_j(t) > P_j^s \end{cases}$$

where $\Delta P_j(t) = P_j^I(t) - P_j^E(t) - P_j^t$, coefficients α_j and β_j are sensitivity constants.

The central summation of mechanoreceptor impulses is modeled using weight coefficients χ_j :

$$N_\Sigma(t) = \sum_{j=1}^4 \chi_j \cdot N_j(t).$$

In neurons of a medulla oblongata, the baroreceptor activity converges with impulses came both through ascending afferent nervous paths from other body structures and through descending nervous paths from supra-bulbar neuronal centers that normally integrate information accepted from external sensors. The model includes two ascending activities presenting the stretch level of skeletal musculature ($N_M(t)$), the hormonal background ($N_H(t)$), and the neuronal activity descending from brain upper structures ($N_B(t)$). In particular, $N_B(t)$ includes the level of the emotional stress. These additional inputs have weight coefficients χ_M , χ_B , and χ_H . $N_\Sigma(t)$ is calculated as:

$$N_\Sigma(t) = \sum_{j=1}^4 \chi_j \cdot N_j(t) + \chi_M \cdot N_M(t) + \chi_H \cdot N_H(t) + \chi_B \cdot N_B(t)$$

Under stable $N_B(t)$, alterations of $N_\Sigma(t)$, as well as alterations of efferent patterns of thus sympathetic ($s_H(t)$) and parasympathetic ($v_H(t)$) nerves display cardiogenic modulations. A flight piloting is specific performance causing psycho-emotional and muscular stress. As these factors are individual for every pilot, the model includes tuning constants for reflecting the individual responses to piloting conditions.

In bulbar cardiovascular neurons, the supra-bulbar neuronal centers have both simulating and inhibiting descending inputs. The resulted dynamics of $N_\Sigma(t)$ determine nervous-reflector corrections of $s_H(t)$, $v_H(t)$, and efferent patterns of sympathetic nerves ($s_V(t)$) altering parameters of compartmental vasculature are calculated using additional weight coefficients χ_M , χ_B , and χ_H in a neuron of the medulla oblongata.

$$E_{HS}(t) = EO_{HS} \cdot (1 - N_\Sigma(t))$$

$$E_{HV}(t) = EO_{HV} \cdot N_\Sigma(t)$$

$$E_{VS}(t) = EO_{VS} \cdot (1 - N_\Sigma(t))$$

Sympathetic ($E_{HS}(t)$) and parasympathetic ($E_{HV}(t)$) influences on chronotropic ($F(t)$) and inotropic ($k(t)$) parameters of the heart are calculated as:

$$T_{FS} \frac{d\Delta F_S}{dt} = K_{FS}(t) \cdot E_{HS}(t) - \Delta F(t)$$

$$T_{FV} \frac{d\Delta F_V}{dt} = K_{FV}(t) \cdot E_{HV}(t) - \Delta F(t)$$

$$T_{kS} \frac{d\Delta k_S}{dt} = K_{kS}(t) \cdot E_{HS}(t) - \Delta k(t)$$

$$T_{kV} \frac{d\Delta k_V}{dt} = K_{kV}(t) \cdot E_{HV}(t) - \Delta k(t)$$

Sympathetic ($E_{VS}(t)$) influences on vascular parameters are calculated as:

$$T_u \frac{d\Delta U}{dt} = \Delta U(t) - K_U(t) \cdot E_{VS}(t)$$

$$T_D \frac{d\Delta D}{dt} = K_D(t) \cdot E_{VS}(t) - \Delta D(t)$$

The resulting nervous control of cardiovascular variables is calculated using constants γ_{Di} and γ_{Ui} that imitate innervation densities in vascular compartments:

$$F(t) = F_a + \Delta F_S(t) - \Delta F_V(t),$$

$$k(t) = F_a + \Delta k_S(t) - \Delta k_V(t),$$

$$D_i(t) = D_{i0} + \gamma_{Di} \cdot \Delta D_i(t),$$

$$U_i(t) = U_{i0} - \gamma_{Ui} \cdot \Delta U_i(t).$$

5. Additional factors modulating the function of CVS under extreme accelerations

In [4], investigators concluded about unpredictability of fighter pilots' G duration by anthropometric and physiological characteristics. Both others [1, 17] had shown that sex, certain anatomical nuances, as well as the sensitivity of CVS to the main hormonal agents modulate the cardiovascular resistance to G_z accelerations. Certainly, these modulations have not been strongly studied. At the same time, approximations proposed in [19] are still the single attempt to model the most characteristic peculiarities of hemodynamics under dynamic positive and negative G_z accelerations. Therefore, these approximations have been included in this version of the model.

Associated reflexes have been modeled by modification of the set-point Y by means of blood catecholamines Y_{cat} , proprioceptor impulses Y_m , and brain generalized pressor reaction Y_{gpr} as:

$$S_{st} = \begin{cases} \mu_{st} \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda t}}{1 + \nu_{st} \cdot e^{-\lambda t}}, & \Delta g > 0 \\ 3\mu_{st} \frac{1 + \eta_{st}(j_s - 1)e^{-\lambda t(t_r - t)}}{1 + \nu_{st} \cdot e^{-\lambda t(t_r - t)}}, & \Delta g \leq 0 \end{cases}, \mu_{st} = \overline{1, 3}. Y_{cat} = Y_{cat}^{\max} \frac{e^{-\omega(T - T_{exp})}}{1 + \phi \cdot e^{-\omega(T - T_{exp})}}$$

$$Y_{gpr} = K_{gpr} \cdot Y \frac{1 - e^{\eta(W_{gpr} - W_0)}}{1 + \nu \cdot e^{\eta(W_{gpr} - W_0)}},$$

$$Y_m = \theta \cdot P_m(t).$$

Three discrete stress levels associated with acceleration direction Δg , sex j_s ($j_s = 1$ - man; $j_s = 2$ - woman) determine the sensitivity to stress S_{st} as:

$$S_{st} = \begin{cases} \mu_{st} \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda t}}{1 + \nu_{st} \cdot e^{-\lambda t}}, & \Delta g > 0 \\ 3\mu_{st} \frac{1 + \eta_{st}(j_s - 1)e^{-\lambda t(t_r - t)}}{1 + \nu_{st} \cdot e^{-\lambda t(t_r - t)}}, & \Delta g \leq 0 \end{cases}, \mu_{st} = \overline{1, 3}.$$

In our simulator, specific program options providing the noted above modifications have to be developed and reflected in the user interface.

Formalisms for models individualization

The equations system described above presents the basic version of the model created for a healthy man with body mass $M = 70\text{ kg}$, height $H = 175\text{ cm}$, and $V_T(t) = 5200\text{ ml}$. The planned simulator will be capable to imitate hemodynamics of both men and women taking into account their individual parameters playing essential role in cardiovascular resistance to G_z accelerations. Using $\psi = M / V_T = 70 / 5200 \approx 0,0135\text{ kg / ml}$, individual total blood volume is calculated as $V_T = \psi \cdot M$. In the basic model, initial $L_i(0)$ were chosen proportional to default value of $H = 175\text{ cm}$. In the individual model, initial $L_i^I(0)$ will be calculated as $L_i^I(0) = H^I \cdot L_i(0) / H$.

Discussion

How to use the model in the future software?

Accelerations are hazardous exposure for many organs and human physiological systems. Safety is the highest priority even during student pilots' training in centrifuges. Usually, the ability to counteract the negative effects of gravitational overloads becomes to future pilots through theory and practice.

There are two groups of tasks to be solved by the simulator based on our model. The first group includes tasks arising under the training. Future fighter pilots are not professionals in human physiology. Therefore, in the theoretical part of the training, the trainer schematically explains the basic physiological processes that impair vision or cause loss of consciousness. In this phase, visual aids may include diagrams demonstrating the blood relocation from the upper body under positive accelerations. Next, the trainer teaches basic techniques to counteract these unwanted changes in blood circulation. At the final stage of pilot training, he is placed in a centrifuge with gradually increasing acceleration. Only at this stage will the future pilot understand from personal experience how successful he is.

The fact is that accelerations are dynamic loads. To effectively counteract them, proper dynamic countermeasures at the right time have to be made. If automatic anti-G devices are used, the algorithm for their activation realizes the due dynamics. However the algorithm is aimed at the average person and the individual reactions of each person may not correspond to the inherent response characteristics. In addition, conscious muscle efforts recommended to counteract the negative effects of acceleration require timely and adequate muscle tension.

So, the main destination of the future software simulator is to visualize both critical hemodynamic characteristics that have to be provided at the due level. The model-based simulator is the sole device illustrating both efficiency of every protection method and best ways for their dynamic combination to reach the needed effect.

We recommend two modes for model use. The first – default mode will provide the trainee with minimal visual information (graphs and a special screen form demonstrating the phenomenon of narrowing the field of view. Up to five graphs will inform the user about the dynamics of the brain and eyes' blood flow, arterial systolic and diastolic pressures, and heart rate in the background of the acceleration profile. The second – advanced mode is addressed to trainers and professionals who try to improve the technology of fighter

pilots resisting accelerations. This type of user can obtain detailed data concerning circulation in every compartment of CVS, the state of nervous-reflector mechanisms, and protection devices.

The system of equations of the model describes the dynamics of physiological processes. The initial values of the model parameters are adjusted to the so-called physiological norm. In this mode, the input influences correspond to the initial state of rest in a human sitting position, and the hemodynamics are stable. In every compartment of the cardiovascular system, there is a balance of input and output blood flows. Here we miss the technology for selecting numerical values of the model parameters. Still, the experience of creating and operating other models (for example, [18-21]) has shown that the models simulate the phenomena under study with acceptable accuracy. The transition process will begin after at least one of the input variables begins to change. There may be a lot of algorithms for these changes. The simulator will provide both a list of algorithms and an opportunity for creating an arbitrary algorithm. Differential equations are solved using a numerical method. Because of the low accuracy of biological measurements used for models of physiological mechanisms, preferable are simple methods (for example, Euler's method). The calculation process ends when the exposure time is reached, or when special situations arise (for example, loss of consciousness, after which the acceleration braking algorithm is launched until the initial level is recovered).

Conclusion

Extreme value and duration dynamic accelerations are the highest degree hazard for both experienced and student pilots. Most data used for developing effective anti-G techniques and technologies concern surface effects. Only rare physiological experiments on animals tried to establish the deep consequences of accelerations [23]. However, animals are not adequate models for this particular exposure. Thus, alternative research approaches are still encouraged. Quantitative mathematical models realized in the form of special software simulators are still a promising alternative. The paper describes a mathematical model as the basis for developing a special computer-based simulator of human physiological reactions to high sustained accelerations. Additional equations needed for modeling of artificial protection tools and methods are presented in recent publication [22]. During creation of these models, the experience obtained earlier and described in [18-21], as well as previous simulators' exploring was used. The modified models will help us in creation of an advanced version of a computer simulator. It can be used both by

future fighter pilots and by physiological-medical experts who attempt to develop advanced and more reliable protection technologies.

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